

Creating and Implementing an Ontology of Texts, Documents and Works in Complex Textual Traditions¹

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Abstract

This article suggests an ontology of texts, documents and works of particular relevance to the editing of complex large textual traditions, such as those of the Greek New Testament (c. 5000 witnesses), Dante's *Commedia* (c. 800) and Chaucer's *Canterbury Tales* (88). The need for this ontology is reviewed through a brief history of the *Canterbury Tales* project's work over three decades, with references also to the Greek New Testament and *Commedia* editorial projects. The central definition of the ontology is that a text is an act of communication inscribed in a document. Further, both the document and the act of communication may be represented as independent and ordered hierarchies of content objects (hence, trees), with textual nodes appearing on both trees, in different orderings and structures across the two trees. The Textual Communities environment successfully implements parts of the ontology of texts, documents and works to enable data collection, management and publication according to the needs of its current users, demonstrating the considerable advantages of this model for textual processing. However, Textual Communities does not implement the whole of this model in terms of data validation, ingestion and processing. Full exploration and implementation of the model here offered are challenges for future scholars. Successful implementation, however, would have considerable benefits, both for scholars working with complex large traditions, and also for those working with smaller but highly complex document sets, such as authorial manuscripts.

1. Background

From the beginnings of what we now call digital humanities, scholars have explored the potential for computers to assist in the handling of complex textual traditions. Indeed, the work of Father Roberto Busa on the text of Aquinas stands as the starting point for this new discipline (Testori 2017). While Busa did not address the question of multiple versions of Aquinas' text, focussing rather on lexical research into an existing established text, other scholars saw the possibility that computers might be applied to the challenging tasks inherent in the making of an edition of a work present in many witnesses. A single glance at the apparatus of a historical edition of a text in many versions, for example, of the sample page of the Nestle-Aland Greek New Testament ("Nestle Aland Novum Testamentum Graece :: Printed Editions" n.d.) calls to mind the labyrinthine patterns of information science: lists, links, hierarchies, complex and regular structures. Here is a suitable subject for the computer. In a lecture at the Clark Library in 1961, Vinton Dearing -- the textual editor of the large multi-volume University of California edition of the works of John Dryden -- compared himself as textual editor, armed with all the latest in

¹ As well as the acknowledgements noted at various points in this article, I owe a special debt to Michael Sperberg-McQueen, Desmond Schmidt, and other participants in the discussion on the Humanist bulletin board in June 2020 of many points raised in this article (Humanist postings 34.89 onwards).

computer tools and techniques, to John Glenn in his space capsule awaiting lift-off: “I am go. All systems are go” (Dearing 1962; 1970) Through the 60s and 70s, Dearing and other scholars created programs for identification of variant texts and for analysis of the variants, to arrive at hypotheses of relations among texts (Gilbert 1973; Petty and Gibson 1970; Hockey 1980).

The arrival of the web in the early 90s, and the advances in digital photography at that time, opened a new possibility. Not only might variants be identified, gathered, stored and analyzed using digital means: everything in the edition could be published digitally. Hence, in just a few years in the 90s, edition projects were announced for works in multiple versions, some of them very large scale (thus, the Blake, Rossetti and Whitman archives; in medieval English my own Canterbury Tales project, the Piers Plowman archive, and the Book of the Duchess: Eaves, Essick, and Viscomi n.d.; McGann 2000; Cohen, Folsom, and Price n.d.; Robinson 1996; “SEENET: Society for Early English and Norse Electronic Texts” n.d.; McGillivray 1997). In this period also the foundations were laid for the full embrace of digital methods by the Greek New Testament editing projects in Birmingham, UK, and Munster, Germany (Houghton et al. 2020). It is notable that most of these projects were led by senior scholars, who early saw the possibilities digital methods offered for their work. These enterprises typically aim to be comprehensive in what they offer: digital images and transcriptions of every page of every document, accompanied by a wide range of tools and editorial materials. Indeed, this inclusiveness has led to questions as to whether these are editions at all, with terms like “archive” often preferred to “edition” (Price 2008; 2009).

Given the significance and scale of these editing projects and their dominance in the landscape of what was then called “Humanities Computing”, it is perhaps surprising that the centre of gravity in the making of scholarly editions has moved since 2000 away from the making of collaborative efforts to explore large textual traditions towards “single-document” editions, which present a digital version of a single document using Textual Encoding Initiative structures. This can be seen in the summary page of Patrick Sahle’s Catalogue of Digital Scholarly Editions: of a total of 607 editions surveyed, 103 are designated as editions of single manuscripts (Sahle 2008). The shift of emphasis towards “single document” publications can be seen in Kevin Kiernan’s concept of the ‘image-based scholarly edition’ and Elena Pierazzo’s advocacy of ‘digital documentary editions (Kiernan 2006; Pierazzo 2011). At the same time, the Joyce scholar Hans Walter Gabler was consciously moving the editorial gaze from “the work” to “the document”. The editor must, he argues, put “the horse of the document before the cart of its eventually emerging text” (Gabler 2007, 201). The revision of the Text Encoding Initiative guidelines (TEI) chapter on “Representation of Primary Sources” reflects this shift, with its opposition of a “documentary transcription”, focussed on a page-by-page representation of the document using the encoding described in that chapter, to a “textual transcription” (“Guidelines – TEI: Text Encoding Initiative” 2007). One can see other indications of this shift. Where the 90s saw the declaration of multiple projects addressing large-scale textual traditions, we have many projects addressing single authorial manuscripts. In the world outside digital humanities, where publishers do continue to print editions of well-known works with large textual traditions behind them (e.g. the plays of Shakespeare and his contemporaries), the focus is on the production of a print edition, with any corresponding digital edition limited in scope to a digital version of the

print with some added tools, and without attempting to match the range of the 1990s endeavours referred to in the last paragraph.²

2. Reinventing the Canterbury Tales project

These changes over three decades – broadly, the move away from the making of large-scale digital editions, accompanied by the shift to online publication of digital editions – presented significant challenges to the Canterbury Tales project, which I had started with others in the early 90s. As early as 1995 the project had arrived at a model for its work and publication which has not changed significantly since. Briefly: the project seeks to transcribe into digital form every page of the 84 pre-1500 manuscripts and 4 incunables which hold texts of Chaucer’s *Canterbury Tales*; to compare the digital transcripts using computer-assisted means to establish a record of agreement and differences at every word in all the witnesses; to analyze the results using a variety of tools (notably phylogenetic methods); and to publish all materials and tools so that others can test and explore beyond our results (Blake and Robinson 1994; 1997). The project’s first publications, with Cambridge University Press up to 2000 and with Scholarly Digital Editions after 2000, were all on CD-ROM, later DVD-ROM. The project published seven CD/DVDs between 1996 and 2010: four presenting sections of the *Tales* in all the manuscripts; two presenting full manuscripts or incunables; one offering a catalogue of all the manuscripts and incunables.

However, as early as the late 90s, it was clear that while our aims had not changed, our methodology for doing and publishing this work would not be able to sustain the project into the future. The *Collate* software (Robinson 1994) at the core of our work relied on the Macintosh Classic environment, and the introduction of Macintosh OS X from 2001 sent a clear signal: the Macintosh Classic environment was dying (Michaels 2002). While a port of *Collate* to OS X was possible, there were other defects in our work processes which ruled out this possibility. *Collate* was conceived before the Web, and accordingly was built for a time when scholars worked off-line, using software on their personal computers to create the files which constituted their work. These files were then passed from person to person, being converted, combined, transformed from stage to stage, through multiple transcripts, then collations, then apparatus files, then phylogenetic files, then all distilled into SGML (later XML) files and passed for a final transformation to a digital publication engine: first Electronic Book Technologies’ DynaText, then later the Anastasia system developed by ourselves. For even one short segment of the *Tales* the number of files generated ran into hundreds, even thousands, distributed across the many computers of the many people working on the project. By 2000 the project was in danger of drowning in its own files, as managing concurrency across many people accessing the same files at the same time became increasingly problematic (cf [Dahlström 2000](#)).

² For example: the online Cambridge University Press edition of Ben Jonson complements and extends the version print in 2012, and is complemented by an extensive range of online materials. See too the rationale given by Linda Bree and James McLaverty for prioritizing the making of a print edition of Jonathan Swift over a digital edition: “a print edition had significant advantages over electronic texts that we did not wish to sacrifice” (Butler, Donaldson, and Bevington 2012; “The Cambridge Edition of the Works of Ben Jonson Online” n.d.; Bree and McLaverty 2009)

Beside the unmanageable glut of files: we had come to see this sequential batch-processing work model as flawed. It depended on a long series of events, from transcription through collation, analysis to publication, with bottle-necks at each point, and with the crippling consequence that a single correction in a single transcription would require traversing the entire series of processes in sequence. Practically, it meant that months, or years, might pass before a transcriber could see how his or her transcription might actually appear. Further, we wanted to move from work on the personal computer, with all the inefficiencies this implied, to a browser-based environment, where anyone in the project could work on any part of it and see the results instantly. Events took a hand. In 2005 the project base moved from De Montfort University to a new Institute for Textual Scholarship and Electronic Editing at the University of Birmingham (“Institute for Textual Scholarship and Electronic Editing - University of Birmingham” n.d.). The key motivation for this move was the recognition that the New Testament digital editing projects associated with Birmingham (and Münster), the Canterbury Tales project, and the Dante editing projects led by Prue Shaw, all faced the same problem (Houghton et al. 2020; Shaw 2006; 2010). All these projects were at that time built on *Collate*; all needed to move to an online browser-based system. The new Birmingham institute promised to provide the resources to create what all these projects needed.

Some parts of what we needed were easily grasped. An online browser environment allowing project partners to view manuscript images page by page, to transcribe each page, and to collate the transcripts online, would take us far towards what we wanted. This architecture assumed that all information would be held in some form of persistent data store on a server backend, with middleware passing information between users working with the browser and data store on the server. This would do away with the whole apparatus of thousands of separate files. Further, this model of browser/middleware/back end is the dominant model (even, the only model) for the structuring of dynamic Web applications, with an immense range of choices at every point of the software cycle.

3. Towards an ontology of texts, documents, works

It is an axiom of information science that before one starts making any kind of data-handling system, that you must understand your data (Simsion and Witt 2005). In 2006, as we reconsidered our working methods, we thought we understood our data. We had carefully-devised protocols of transcription, which we expressed in TEI XML (Robinson and Solopova 1993). We had settled on a section by section, line by line encoding which allowed us to label every section of Chaucer’s text, in every witness, so we could extract all versions of any line for collation, again using TEI protocols. Indeed, we had re-lineated the whole of the *Tales*, following a system devised by Norman Blake (Blake 1997). Further, we had devised a scheme for dealing with the difficulty of showing page-by-page transcriptions of sections of the poem which span across page boundaries. This had meant confronting a well-known characteristic of the “Ordered Hierarchy of Content Objects” (OHCO) model underlying Standard Generalized Markup Language (SGML) encoding, and its successor, eXtensible Markup Language (XML). Both SGML and XML permit full encoding of a single hierarchy of content objects, while offering the possibility of signalling other kinds of division through “milestone” elements. For the *Canterbury Tales*, as for the Dante and Greek New Testament projects, we chose to make the primary hierarchy the division into separate segments corresponding with long-recognized parts

of the *Tales* (the *Knight's Tale* etc. and associated link passages), with each section further divided into verse lines or prose segments. Because we wanted to show transcriptions by document page, and to show the page image next to the page transcription, we marked the beginning of each page in the transcription file with an empty `<pb/>` element. From 1998 on, I developed a publication system that, in essence, had a full understanding of the primary hierarchy of *Tales* and links/verse lines and prose segments, and understood too enough of the use of milestones to mark page breaks to be able to show transcripts by page and to align the transcripts with page images. This was the Anastasia publishing system (Robinson 2001; 2004). This proved adequate for the Chaucer and Dante publications of Scholarly Digital Editions between 2000 and 2010, and for the first digital prototype publications of the Greek New Testament (Institute for New Testament Research, Münster, Germany 2003). However, the Anastasia system was built on the same model of sequential batch processing as the whole *Collate* based software suite. We would have to discard this too as we moved towards a real-time online set of editing tools.

The need to create a new system also gave us an opportunity to reconsider our data model. In essence, our data model saw the text as a single continuous stream. This single stream was explicitly structured into ordered content objects, organized into a hierarchy within a SGML/XML tree. In addition, segments of the single stream were marked by milestone elements, representing sequences of pages. Many other systems designed for handling textual data for scholarly editions followed a similar model, under the shorthand rubric of “overlapping hierarchies”: thus “stand-off markup” and various implementations in systems such as ‘Just-in-time trees’, ‘Just-in-time markup’, and (most elaborately, in terms of document markup) in ‘Trojan Horse markup’.³ Many people, beside ourselves, found this model sufficient for their immediate purposes. One could process the single continuous stream with a standard SGML/XML tool to extract the entire “primary” tree. Simultaneously, or separately, one could process the single continuous stream to identify the milestone or other elements embedded within it to identify other meaningful document regions. For a long time this model served all our needs, as it did for many others. However, two factors led us to see this model as inadequate.

³ The literature on coping with multiple structures within a structured text framework is copious, with over 30 articles on the topic “Concurrent Markup/Overlap” listed in the Balisage Series on Markup Technologies index (“Balisage Series on Markup Technologies. Topic: Concurrent Markup/Overlap” 2020). The OHCO thesis was stated and elaborated in a series of publications from 1987 to 1993, with later publications qualifying and extending the 1987 ‘single-structure’ hypothesis to accommodate multiple structures (Coombs, Renear, and DeRose 1987; DeRose et al. 1990; Renear, Mylonas, and Durand 1993; cf. McGann 2004). ‘Just-in-time-trees’ (Durusau and O’Donnell 2002); ‘Just in time Markup’ in scholarly editions (Eggert et al. 2002) and “Trojan horse markup” (S. DeRose 2004) are only a few of the work-arounds addressing this problem.

Figure 1. Folio 17r, base of first column, of Biblioteca Nacional de España (BNE) MS 5795

The first factor was that in our everyday work with many documents we kept seeing phenomena such as shown in Figure 1, at the base of the first column of folio 17r of manuscript BNE 5795 of the *Estoria de España* of Alfonso X. The text at the right, appearing red in the manuscript and here set in three boxes, is the rubric for what modern editors identify as Chapter 40 of the *Estoria España*.⁴ The two-line high initial M at the left marks the beginning of chapter 40. One can see what the scribe did, and why he or she did it. The text is written in a regular two columns. The problem for the scribe, as he or she was writing this column, was that the standard two-line height of the initial marking the beginning of the next chapter had to appear at the beginning of the second-last line of the column, to conform with the pattern established elsewhere in the manuscript. It could not appear at the beginning of the last line, as that would mean the bottom half of the two-line M appearing outside the ruled writing space and intruding into the bottom margin always kept clear of any text. There was not space to finish the preceding chapter (concluding with the words “τ fue cōtra Sçipio”), write the rubric and the opening words of Chapter 40 (beginning “Miētre q̄”), and have the next chapter start on the second-last line. The scribe’s solution was ingenious. He or she split the rubric into three parts. He or she wrote the first two words of the rubric “De coño” in red after the last words of the previous chapter (the top box in the figure); wrote the next words of the rubric “lidiarō τ fue añjbal ueçi” in red at the end of the next line (the middle box), after the first words of the next chapter, and then wrote the final syllable of the rubric “do” in red at the very end of the last line of the column, after the next words of the beginning of the new chapter (the bottom box). This writing sequence challenges the model of a single stream of text. The scribe has split the rubric into three parts, and then broken up the writing of the end of one chapter and the beginning of the next by planting the three parts in three different places. Of course, after years of resourceful encoding and scripting, we had figured out how to process such phenomena more or less successfully. None the less, our confidence in our model was disturbed by the recurrence of such instances.

⁴ This example with associated transcriptions is from the Birmingham digital edition of the *Estoria España* ([Estoria de Espanna Digital](#).)

The second factor was that in this period I was engaging in a years-long discussion with textual scholars interested in theory who, like me, found themselves questioning whether long-held understandings of the fundamental concepts of textual scholarship remained valid in the digital age. These scholars were Peter Shillingsburg, Paul Eggert, Hans Walter Gabler and Barbara Bordalejo. This discussion began around 1990, when I first met Shillingsburg, expanded in 1991 when I met Eggert and Gabler, and then again in 1999 when Bordalejo joined the Canterbury Tales project.⁵ Our discussions focussed on three words: texts, documents, works. Textual scholarship, in every discipline, is built on an understanding of those three words. In normal speech, we may use the word “text” to refer to anything written, spoken, or thought: to anything from a specific document (the text of the Hengwrt manuscript) to some kind of notion of an abstract authorial object divorced from any one document (the text of “Hamlet”). No model of textual scholarship can be built on such elastic meanings. The digital turn gave our deliberations particular urgency, with all of us variously involved in digital edition projects. I have already quoted Gabler’s formulation of the relationship between text and document. However, while Gabler stresses the importance of the document, he also asserts the importance of the work (“It is the purpose of the edition, and I believe the duty, to mediate the work” – email to the author 17 December 2012). While some textual scholars appear to want to remove the work from textual scholarship as a “manifestly relegated term” (Sutherland 1996), for us the “work” remained central to textual scholarship. But how should we define these three fundamental terms?⁶

4. An ontology of texts, documents and works

⁵ The most accessible record of these discussions is in the essays by all five scholars in a special section of *Ecdotica*, edited by Bordalejo ([Bordalejo 2013a](#); [Robinson 2013](#); [Gabler 2013](#); [Eggert 2013](#); [Bordalejo 2013b](#); [Shillingsburg 2013](#); see also [Eggert 2009](#); [Gabler 2010](#); [2012](#); [Robinson 2012](#); [Shillingsburg 1986](#); [2006](#)). Over many conference presentations, conversations and emails, significant additional contributions were made by Lou Burnard, Zeth Green, David Greetham, Jerome McGann, Federico Meschini, David Parker, Desmond Schmidt, Michael Sperberg-McQueen and Klaus Wachtel. Articles and books by Greetham, McGann, Donald McKenzie (Greetham 1999; McGann 1983; McKenzie 1986) and – especially – Thomas Tanselle (1992) were also influential.

⁶ Several other systems address the same problem, of creating a model of documents, works and texts useful for scholarship in the digital age. The Federated Requirements for Bibliographic Records (FRBR) scheme establishes a fundamental architecture in which some parts of the ontology described in the next section fit neatly, with ‘work’ (or a top-level ‘entity’) corresponding to ‘work’ in FRBR (Standing Committee of the IFLA Section on Cataloguing 1998). Similarly, a ‘document’ may be either a FRBR ‘manifestation’ or ‘item’. The capacity of the ontology here described to manage objects below the level of whole work and document suggests that the model of text given in the next section could be used to extend FRBR-compatible catalogue entries. Canonical Text Services (CTS; formerly Classical Text services) seeks to align itself with FRBR, and to extend FRBR to identification and retrieval of passages of text (“An Overview of CTS URNs” n.d.). CTS explicitly supports hierarchical models and speaks of “works” in ways closely paralleling the definition given in the next section. However, “text” is used variously, sometimes to identify it with a particular document (“exemplar” in CTS/FRBR language), at other times with versions of the act of communication, as “edition” and “version”, and there seems no native understanding in CTS that a document is itself a hierarchy. The Scholarly Commentaries and Texts Archive (SCTA) also seeks to extend FRBR, appears to provide finer-grained access to documents (to the level of the line space) than does CTS, and also offers full semantic web access through RDF and linked data. However, its model of text is limited (basically prose texts, using TEI <p> elements) and the depth of its support for document hierarchies and for overlap of these with other hierarchies is unclear (“Scholarly Commentaries and Texts Archive” n.d.) The system here described differs from both in that it does not attempt to align itself with FRBR, concentrating instead on the parts of document, text and work below the FRBR’s “item” or “manifestation” level.

Underlying all three terms, and the whole of textual scholarship, is the concept of an act of communication. Eggert has underlined this elegantly in his discussion of the marks on a tree left by burrowing insects: in their squiggles and flourishes, these marks look as if they could be some form of writing, carved by some person on the tree (Eggert 2010).⁷ But they are not human writing and they do not represent an act of human communication. Other people, experts in trees or insects or ecology, might be interested in these marks. But we are textual scholars, we are interested in acts of human communication. An act of communication can only become a communication when it assumes some physical form, accessible to some other person apart from the person who originated it.

Hence, the key definition, the first axiom of this ontology:

1. A text is an act of communication inscribed in a document

This definition might be said to be a tautology: an act of communication must have some physical form, if only the sounds of a human voice. However, it is useful to spell this out for two reasons. The first reason: there is a common tendency to speak of text as if it can exist without any physical form, apart from any document: “the text of the Greek New Testament”. There is no such thing as a text without a document. An act of communication cannot exist without some kind of physical form. This is particularly true of the kinds of communications with which textual scholars deal. We are interested in communications expressed in some symbolic form: usually language, as words, but also musical and mathematical notation. Most commonly we find these acts of communication in written form: our documents are usually manuscripts or print books (though they might also be sound or video recordings, and are increasingly streams of characters on computer screens). All these are documents holding acts of communications. These are texts.

The second reason this definition has to be explicit is to underline that not everything in a document is a text. There may be discolorations, worm holes, various scribal marks as pen trials, or marks of rulings. If these are not identified as potential acts of communication (see further below), they are not texts, any more than the insect marks in Eggert’s example are texts. Or, the scholar might identify parts of the document as containing acts of communication in which he or she is not interested.

Hence: every text has a twofold aspect. It is both an act of a communication, and it is the particular document in which that text is inscribed (Robinson 2012). A second axiom of this ontology:

2. Both the act of communication and the document may be represented as an ordered hierarchy of content objects

⁷ Behind Eggert’s lucid exposition is Shillingsburg’s identification of ‘script acts’ as the base material of textual scholarship: thus his description of digital editions as “an electronic infrastructure for representing script acts” (Shillingsburg 2006), chapter four. The label “script acts” acknowledges the debt to speech act theory, as developed by John Searle and J.L. Austin, itself resting on thinking by Russell and Wittgenstein (Austin 1962; Searle 1969; Green 2017)

For each act of communication: every story has a beginning, a middle, an end; a Shakespeare play is divided into acts, scenes, lines; the Bible is divided into testaments, books, chapters, verses; Dante's *Commedia* into canticles, cantos, lines. Beside our own intuition, explicit statements affirm "Here begins.." and "Here ends", and complex mise-en-page forms, all witness elaborate structures. We may argue about how any act of communication should be structured, but the reality of structure is part of our communication. For every document: a whole physical book is divided into quires; the quires are made up of pages; the pages composed of multiple writing-spaces, in columns, in margins, in headers and footers, with spaces for lines of text embedded in the writing spaces. Both act of communication and document may be efficiently and completely represented in a tree, and hence in XML.⁸

Notoriously, the two hierarchies – of the act of communication and of the document – almost never coincide in their structures. A long novel may span multiple volumes; a chapter, a paragraph, a sentence, even a word, might be split across a page or a column or a line. Usually this is formulated as "overlapping hierarchies". But as the example of the three-part rubric from the *Estoria España* suggests, the relationship between the two hierarchies is not that they are different segmentations of a single stream of text. There is no "single stream of text". Instead we have a pool of textual nodes. The textual nodes may appear in radically different orders on the two trees.⁹ Here, in the act of communication tree, the three parts of the rubric are a single branch, labelled as the initial rubric of chapter 40, following the last segment of chapter 39. However, in the document tree the three parts appear on three separate branches: one at the end of the third-last line of the column; the second at the end of the second-last line, the third at the end of the last line of the column. Note too that in this formulation it does not matter where the document places these nodes. An author might split the writing of an additional section of text across multiple pages, even writing the last part on an earlier page: the section will still form a single node in the act of communication tree.

Hence our third and fourth axioms:

3. *The act of communication and the document trees are distinct and independent*
4. *The textual nodes may be seen as a collection of leaves, with each leaf present on both trees*

⁸ The TEI discrimination between the use of the "<text>" element to present the act of communication as the primary hierarchy and the "<sourceDoc>" and "<facsimile>" elements to present the disposition of the text on the document as the primary hierarchy maps to this double aspect of text as act of communication and document inscription.

⁹ A key moment in my recognition of the importance of different orderings was a conversation with Klaus Wachtel c. 1999, in which he explained some of the problems related to the pericope of the "Woman taken in Adultery" (Keith 2008; Knust and Wasserman 2018). This pericope is absent in the oldest Greek New Testament witnesses; appears at John 7:53-8:11 in most modern editions and in many manuscripts; appears after John 21:25 in some manuscripts; after Luke 24:53 and 21:38 in others; is marked as an addition in some witnesses, and marked for deletion in others; is cited or quoted in other texts, including a crucial citation by Eusebius of a lost text of Papias, which would date knowledge of the pericope as early as c. 110 c.e. Accordingly, a model of text was needed that would permit unambiguous identification and retrieval of all versions of this pericope from every document, wherever it appears, however it is revised. This model enables that.

Thus in the *Estoria España* example: from the document tree we can readily extract the leaves to show the textual content of the last three lines of the column (as indeed, the whole column, and the whole page). From the act of communication tree we can readily extract the text of the end of Chapter 39, the initial rubric of Chapter 40 (as a single sequence of text), and the beginning of Chapter 40.

We now turn to definition of the “work.” James McLaverty’s paraphrase of F. W. Bateson sets out the challenge: “If the Mona Lisa is in the Louvre, where are *Hamlet* and *Lycidas*?” (Bateson 1961; McLaverty 1984). My answer (which is also the answer of Tanselle, Eggert, Shillingsburg and of many others) is the same as McLaverty’s: they are to be found in all the documents. When we say “the text of the Greek New Testament” we are using a shorthand for “the Greek New Testament as we know it from all the documents which contain what we recognize as all or part of it.”¹⁰ There is no Platonic or immaterial “work”. There are only documents, in which we see what we recognize as acts of communication. The basis of textual scholarship is that instances of what we identify as an act of communication may occur in multiple documents. We see what we call “Shakespeare’s *Hamlet*” in two quarto editions and in the first folio, and then in multiple copies of these; we see what we call “the Greek New Testament” in Codex Sinaiticus and Codex Vaticanus; what we call “Chaucer’s *Canterbury Tales*” in the Hengwrt and Ellesmere manuscripts. In Eggert’s formulation, the work is a “regulative idea”, a useful way of specifying that the different texts of the different editions of *Hamlet* may be aligned and compared for multiple purposes (Eggert 2009, 234–35). I take this a step further, to emphasize that in the context of medieval and ancient texts one is exploring the relationships between multiple texts. Thus:

5. *A work is a set of texts which is hypothesized as organically related, in terms of the acts of communication which they present*

We hypothesize that 88 pre-1500 witnesses present variant texts of what we label as Geoffrey Chaucer’s *Canterbury Tales* (but which was actually known, until well after this date, as *The Book of the Tales of Canterbury*). We can further divide this act of communication into a hierarchy of multiple ordered acts of communication (labelled as the *General Prologue*, the *Knight’s Tale*), and divide these again into yet smaller ordered acts of communication (labelled as lines 1 and 2) which we can then identify as present in multiple documents and compare with one another.

We have, up to this point, been speaking as if the text present at corresponding nodes of the document and act of communication hierarchy were always identical. Very often it is: we might expect that the text as printed on the page of a book will be identical in the record of the act of communication. But in many cases it will not be identical:

6. *At each textual node, the text as recorded in the document may differ from the text as recorded in the act of communication*

¹⁰ A key factor in my recognition that works exist only in the documents we have was David Parker’s declaration that the New Testament is the “tradition”: the documents we have from the beginnings to the present and all that we understand from them (Parker 1991; 1997).

There are many reasons why the texts may differ. First, the text of the document may correspond to what scholars of *critique génétique* call the “avant-texte”: as explained by Daniel Ferrer, the set of marks found in the document are to be seen as a “protocol for making a text” (Ferrer 1998, 261). For any one set of marks in the document, multiple transcriptions are possible, according to how the transcriber interprets the protocol and the purposes of the transcription, as may be seen in the ‘topographic’ and ‘linear’ transcriptions defined by the Samuel Beckett Archive (“Samuel Beckett: Digital Manuscript Project” n.d.). Outside the domain of modern authorial texts, in the context of medieval manuscripts, Bordalejo uses the term “the text of the document” to describe “the sequence of letters and meaningful marks the reader sees on the page”(Bordalejo 2010). One may stress the word “meaningful”: different readers will find different meanings. Secondly, the text of the act of communication, as determined by the transcriber/editor, is the result of interpretation. Multiple editorial judgements will here intervene. Bordalejo gives this example, from the Riccardiana ms. 1005 of Dante’s *Inferno* iii, 8:

Figure 2. The last word of Dante *Inferno* iii, 8 in Riccardiana ms. 1005.

Here, one can see the first three letters “dur”, then the letter “a” with an underdot beneath it, followed by an “o”. This sequence may be recorded as the “text of the document.” However, the editor Shaw determined that the scribe first wrote “dura”, then realized from the rhyme words “oscuro” and “duro” in lines 10 and 12 that the last letter should be “o”, so changed the word to “duro” by marking the “a” for deletion by an underdot and writing “o” after it. Hence, the “text of the document” might be represented as “duṙao”, while the editor might deduce variant acts of communication: an original reading of “dura” and an altered reading “duro”.

5. Implementing the ontology: the naming of parts

In our implementation, we replace the term “work”, used in the previous section, by the more neutral term “entity”, to denote a discrete act of communication. Each constituent part of the ontology – each document and every part of each document, each entity and every part of every entity, every text – must be addressable by a unique name. These names are formulated according to the Kahn/Wilensky architecture, of a naming authority followed by key/value pairs, and implemented in URN-like syntax compatible with the semantic web (Kahn and Wilensky 2006). Thus:

```
urn:det:tc:usask:CTP2/document=Hengwrt
```

We have declared the URN scheme ‘det’ (for “Documents, Entities and Texts”). The sequence “tc:usask:CTP2” declares the naming authority. The name itself is given as a key/value pair, “document=Hengwrt”. Because the document is seen, in our system, as a tree object, we can use an XPath-like syntax to drill down to each part of the document:

```
document=Hengwrt:folio=1r:line=2
```

indicates the second line space of folio 1r of the Hengwrt manuscript. Similarly, the act of communication (entity) of *the Canterbury Tales* is represented as:

entity=CT

Again, as the entity is seen as a tree object, we can use an XPath-like syntax to drill down to each part of the act of communication:

entity=CT:part=GP:line=1

indicates the first line of the General Prologue of the *Canterbury Tales*.

We have defined a text as an act of communication (entity) inscribed in a document. Accordingly, collocation of the act of communication and of the document specifies the text of this act of communication in this document:

entity=CT:part=GP:line=1:document=Hengwrt:folio=1r:line=2

indicates the first line of the General Prologue of the *Canterbury Tales* as it appears in the second line space of folio 1r of the Hengwrt manuscript. Note that this system manages text which is repeated, transposed, or otherwise multiply dislocated in a document. For example, entity=CT:part=GP:line=1:document=Hengwrt:folio=200r:line=30 would specify the text of the first line of the General Prologue as it appears in line space 30 of folio 200r.

Where an act of communication spans across document elements, this can be specified as follows:

entity=CT:part=GP:line=1:document=Hengwrt:folio=1r:line=3

indicates the part of the first line of the General Prologue of the *Canterbury Tales* as it appears in the third line space of folio 1r of the Hengwrt manuscript (in fact, the first line is written in a single space.)

The utility of this system may be readily grasped. One can identify, and reliably extract, the following:

- The text of any particular act of communication in any particular part of any document (thus: the form of the first line of the *Tales* as it appears on the first page of the Hengwrt manuscript)
- The text of all instances of any particular act of communication in any particular document (thus: all forms of the first line of the *Tales* as it appears in any part of the Hengwrt manuscript)
- The text of all instances of any particular act of communication in any document (thus: all forms of the first line of the *Tales* as it appears in any manuscript)
- For any line space on any page of any document: identify the acts of communication recorded within that line and return the text

- For any page of any document: identify the acts of communication recorded within that page, within all the line spaces on that page, and return the text
- For any document: identify all the acts of communication recorded within that document, with the exact pages and line spaces in which they appear
- For any act of communication: identify all the documents and all pages and line spaces in those documents which contain instances of that act of communication.

This model is able to deal with both duplicate and discontinuous acts of communication within any document, and between documents. In the *Canterbury Tales* we can identify verse lines which are repeated on different pages, or which are transposed, or divided. A newspaper story might be split across multiple sections and pages. An author might write one version of a paragraph across several pages, and then mark it all for deletion, then write another version across several pages, and yet another version in another part of the document. These instances of this act of communication in all the separate documents can be identified, found and used.

It is a significant advantage that this model applies to two types of scholarly edition, usually distant from each other: editions of large textual traditions, such as those of the Greek New Testament and of the *Canterbury Tales*, and editions of complex document sets, such as heavily revised authorial manuscripts. Indeed, as the two types overlap (many manuscripts of the *Canterbury Tales* show multiple scribal revision; as well as the authorial document there may be many published witnesses), it is critical that the one model is valid in both contexts.

6. Implementing the Ontology: Textual Communities, 2010-

By 2010 we had an early version of the ontology described in the previous sections, as presented by Robinson and Meschini at the 2010 ADHO conference (Robinson and Meschini 2010; Robinson 2017); see Parker for an early invocation of this ontology (2012, 10–14, 29). Sample Protégé-compatible files implementing the ontology in OWL, RDF and XML format are available (Robinson 2020). In 2010, I and the *Canterbury Tales* project moved to the University of Saskatchewan. A key motivation for this move was the possibility of significant support for the making of an online collaborative editing system capable of doing what the project needed, built on the model of text we were developing. This is the Textual Communities system, built with support from the Canada Foundation of Innovation, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada and the University of Saskatchewan from 2010 on.

Because two parts of our model of text may be expressed as ordered hierarchies of content objects, an obvious route was to use an XML database. Our first attempt in 2007 at a replacement for the Anastasia system used the XML-DB database, otherwise “Berkeley DB XML” and now part of Oracle corporation (“Berkeley DB XML | Database | Oracle” n.d.). However, we found significant performance problems with this even before coming to Canada. Were we starting now, we might use eXist, but around 2011 this did not seem sufficiently developed to carry the weight of data with which we knew we had to deal. Because we had an ontology, we experimented with OWL/RDF based systems, such as SPARQL. Again, we found significant performance issues, and again we were concerned with how the system would scale with our data.

The architecture of unique identifiers linking multiple sets of data looked, to us in 2011, like something which would fit well in a relational database. At the same time, our colleagues in the New Testament projects, especially Troy Griffiths, had chosen a combination of LifeRay “social media” software, for user management and the browser environment, and a MySQL database for backend datastore and retrieval. The first version of Textual Communities (2011-2018) was built on these same pillars. However, by 2014 we were aware of problems with this combination. Where the New Testament projects were able to define in advance how their data was structured and tune the database accordingly, we intended Textual Communities to deal with any TEI/XML document. As we explored SQL relational databases, we faced increasingly complex problems as we dealt with diverse data collections. Especially, we began to find indexing and retrieval activities could be lengthy and require complex SQL queries, so putting in question the aim of a sustainable, interactive and dynamic editorial environment. Hence, from 2014 on, we shifted the whole of Textual Communities in a completely different direction. First, we chose to use a JSON document database, MongoDB, as a backend for all data. Our initial experiments showed that, firstly, we could represent everything in our XML documents within the JSON database, and then remake the XML without any loss of information. Secondly, the flexibility of JSON meant that we could create a collection of JSON documents which implemented the architecture of text as a collection of leaves with each leaf present in two distinct tree structures. Thirdly, we could do this in a way by which retrieval insertion, deletion and updating of documents would be fast enough to work interactively over the web. We then married the JSON backend, using Node for the server software, to a frontend using the Angular framework to build the user environment. This meant that every part of the system was using Javascript as the programming language, which considerably eased our work.

I here summarize the structure of the MongoDB database underlying all our work, implementing the text/entity/document ontology described earlier. The basis unit of MongoDB is the ‘document’, representing a single JSON object. In our system, there are three MongoDB collections of documents, as follows.

1. The *documents* collection. Each “document” in our hierarchy, and every part of every “document”, is represented by a MongoDB document within the *documents* collection. Each such document has a label and is embedded in a hierarchy, with one field listing all the ancestors of this document, and another field listing all the children of this document, in order. The ancestors and children are listed by the MongoDB identifier of each of these documents. Thus, for folio 1r of the Hengwrt manuscript, the MongoDB document representing folio 1r appears as follows:
name: “1r”,
ancestors: *ObjectId of the document representing the whole Hengwrt manuscript*,
children: *ObjectIds of the documents representing each line space on this page*
2. The *entities* collection. Each act of communication, and every part of every act of communication, is represented by a MongoDB document within the *entities* collection. Each such document is embedded in a hierarchy, with one field listing all the ancestors of this entity, and another field listing all the children of this entity, in order. The ancestors and children are listed by the MongoDB identifier of each of these documents. Thus, for

the *Canterbury Tales*, the document representing the *General Prologue* appears as follows:

name: “GP”,
ancestors: *ObjectId of the document representing the whole Canterbury Tales*,
children: *ObjectIds of the documents representing each line of the Prologue*

3. The *teis* collection. Each document within the *teis* collection corresponds to a single object in the TEI/XML document holding both the text of the document and the text of the act of communication inscribed in that document. This permits full reconstruction of each TEI/XML document from this collection alone. Within the *teis* collection, the fundamental documents are those which represent the leaves holding the text. Here are the key fields, for the first line of the *General Prologue* of the *Canterbury Tales*, as it appears in the second line-space of folio 1r of the Hengwrt manuscript:

name: “#text”,
text: “Whan that Aprille with his shoures sote”,
ancestors: *ObjectIds of the entities (acts of communication) containing this text expressed hierarchically, up to the root: line 1, of the General Prologue, of the Canterbury Tales*,
docs: *ObjectIds of the document parts containing this text expressed hierarchically, up to the root: the second line-space, on folio 1r, of the Hengwrt manuscript*

A fuller account of the structure of the MongoDB documents collection, with more detail on how (for example) text leaves which span several documents and entities are treated, can be found in the paper given by me at the ADHO 2018 conference in Mexico City (Robinson 2019). There is a demonstration version of Textual Communities at www.textualcommunitiesandbox.org, and a full production version at www.textualcommunities.org. A public API has been created for Textual Communities (Robinson 2018). Using this API, one can (for example) retrieve our transcription of folio 1r of the Hengwrt manuscript with this address:

<https://textualcommunities.org/uri/urn:det:tc:usask:CTP2/document=Hg:folio=1r?type=transcript&format=html>

The API is used to make a full publication in Tom Farrell’s edition of the *Tales of the Reeve and Cook* (Farrell Forthcoming). In summary: the Textual Communities implementation of this ontology, flawed as it is (see next section), satisfies the basic needs of the *Canterbury Tales* and similar projects. We can view, assign, manage and update manuscript transcripts page-by-page. We can retrieve all the versions of any one line of the *Tales* from all the documents and collate them, using an adaptation of the Collation Editor, itself built on CollateX (Smith [2018] 2020; Dekker and Middell [2010] 2020), no matter where and how the versions appear in the documents. We can extract what is needed for a publication through the public API.

7. The next steps

While Textual Communities is now stable and meeting the foreseeable needs of the Canterbury Tales Project for all parts of our work, from transcription through collation and analysis to

publication, there are multiple areas where the implementation of the model of documents, works and texts which we have developed is deficient. First, it should be underlined that it was not until 2018 – well into the implementation here described – that I formulated five of the axioms given in section 4 above. Indeed, axiom six (that at each textual node, the text of the document and the text of the act of communication might differ) only became clear to me in the course of the discussion on Humanist referred to in footnote 1. We were trying to design, build and fly an aeroplane all at the same time. On looking back, we would have built our core MongoDB tables rather differently. Indeed, we might have chosen to use eXist or another XML database rather than JSON and MongoDB. Alternatively, the maturing of the “semantic web” might lead us to go down the rdf/linked data path (cf. the successful use of this technology by (“Scholarly Commentaries and Texts Archive” n.d.) We were also focussed on just two hierarchies: that of the document and that of the act of communication. There can be many more than just two hierarchies for any text, and a full implementation would take that into account, as we did not.

The greatest area of weakness in our implementation is document ingestion. We use TEI/XML to encode our documents for loading into Textual Communities and for encoding all page-by-page transcriptions. As a result, we are limited because XML can recognize only one hierarchy of content objects. Because we are dealing with multiple witnesses to acts of communication, we choose to make that our primary hierarchy. As we load each document and each page of transcription, we must infer the document hierarchy from the sequence of empty “milestone” elements marking pages, columns and line breaks (<pb/> <cb/> <lb/>). We are not able to deal with the kinds of complex document segmentation handled by (for example) the TEI/XML <sourceDoc> element. One could go some way to mimicking the functioning of <sourceDoc> and its children by ingenious use of milestone elements, as in DeRose’s “trojan horse” architecture (2004). However, this would still fall far short of the documents, works and texts model here developed. The fundamental problem with our work process at present is that we load and parse each document, and each part of each document, as a single stream of text, because in our original model, that is what we thought text was. This runs counter to the model by which leaves of text may be quite differently distributed across the two trees: text continuously written in the document may represent discontinuous and radically dispersed acts of communication. In our current implementation we use various cunning devices to compensate for this deficiency (e.g. using the TEI pointer attribute “next” to link parts of an act of communication which are split across the document, as in the *Estoria España* example). We should not have to resort to such remedies.¹¹

Another area of weakness is that our implementation does not cope natively with the situation where the text of the document and the text of the act of communication diverge. Once more, in Textual Communities we deploy various ad hoc workarounds, so that our interfaces and publications do offer the reader the choice of seeing divergent texts. Once more, these are awkward fixes, forced on us because our implementation does not realize our model. There is also a need to explore fully the applicability of this model to a second type of scholarly edition, that of smaller but highly-complex sets of documents, as in heavily-revised authorial manuscripts.

¹¹ Several publications in *Balisage* dealing with concurrent/overlap (“Balisage Series on Markup Technologies. Topic: Concurrent Markup/Overlap” 2020) propose schemes to manage such discontinuities (Sperberg-McQueen and Huitfeldt 2008; Portier and Calabretto 2009).

Looking back over thirty years of work, I can see that I fell into a familiar trap. I wanted to make something that did what I wanted, and I built it a piece at a time. Along the way, I constructed a theory to explain what I was doing, as I saw it in the moment. I now see that the theory was founded on an incomplete model of text. This recognition came too late in our work for us to be able to base what we did fully on our new understanding. It did not mean we could not achieve our aims, but it made our work more difficult than it should have been. It would be useful if others could begin where we finished. Full implementation of this model would make it possible for more scholars to work productively in large textual traditions. Further, as this model applies also to texts in smaller but highly-complex sets of documents, such as heavily-revised authorial manuscripts, it will enable editions of these also.

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